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Earners of this certification have an in-depth understanding of AWS machine learning (ML) services. They demonstrated ability to build, train, tune, and deploy ML models using the AWS Cloud. Badge owners can derive insight from AWS ML services using either pretrained models or custom models built from open-source frameworks.

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